

STATE, TRAIT, OR INTEGRATE: EXPLAINING TRAJECTORIES, TRANSITIONS, AND
TURNING POINTS OF CRIMINAL BEHAVIOR AND DEVIANCE
OVER THE LIFE COURSE

By

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A Research Paper

For

SOC 9094 – Directed Research

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3/25/2026METHODS

Participants and Data Sources

The subjects used in this study were 1173 offenders who were placed on probation in a Central Minnesota community between 2002 and 2006. Corrections officials interviewed the offenders about various facets of their local life circumstances, and also collected data about previous convictions, current offenses, birthdates, gender, etc. A follow-up interview was given an average of six-months later, resulting in an opportunity for a longitudinal analysis of data. The data sources used in this study consisted of the interview records, Bureau of Criminal Apprehension (BCA) arrest and conviction records, and Court Services parole violation records resulting in a commitment to prison.

Sample selection. To avoid undercounting conviction and parole violations, only data from interviews done from 2002 through 2004 were used in the study phase. This allowed for the analysis of 12-month recidivism rates with an additional year from the end of the study period for any violations to turn into convictions and be entered into the BCA database. It is assumed that most violations come to trial and turn into convictions within 1 year after the violation date. The sample in this study used consists of the interview records of all of the offenders with two assessments completed before 2005.

Sample demographic data. The sample consisted of 1173 offenders with a mean age of 34.25. 83% of the sample was male. The racial distribution was 81% white and 19% other races who were predominantly black.

Sample Risk Level. The mean risk level, as measured using the LSI-R, for this sample was compared with national norms and plotted in Figure 1. The sample is comparable to the prison norm on the high and low ranges and has slightly lower LSI-R risk scores for the midrange, which also includes most offenders.

Figure 1

Risk Level of Offender Sample Compared with National Prison and Corrections Norms

Data Variables

The dependent variable used in this study, called Violation, was coded a one if either a felony arrest leading to conviction or a probation violation leading to incarceration occurred within one year of the assessment. While probation violation is not as serious as a felony arrest, there was no way to determine whether the offender would have offended if he or she had not been sent to prison for the probation violation. The independent variables used in this study were age at assessment completion, sex, race, total previous offenses, total current offenses, employment status, financial status, social assistance status, and attitude supportive of crime. A

composite variable, called TotCrim was created from the sum of the total previous offenses and the total current offenses. This is a ratio variable that ranges from 0 to 189, with a mean of 7.9, a mode of 5 and a median of 6. Variables representing change in job status were also created, LostJob, GotJob, and HadJob to represent losing a job, getting a job, and keeping a job between interviews. Interaction terms, TotCrimXlj, TotCrimXgj, and TotCrimXhj were created by multiplying TotCrim by LostJob, GotJob, and HadJob respectively.

Rational for variable selection. The variables used in this study were chosen for the following reasons.

1. Violation: The sum of previous offenses and current offenses gives a reasonable estimation of the level of self-control the offender possesses. As Hirschi (????) has claimed many times, the strongest indicator of future offending is past offending.
2. Employment Status: One of the main contentions of life-course theorists such as Sampson and Laub (????) is that employment may reduce the level of offending.
3. Change/Continuity of Employment: Are changes in employment status the same as having the same status?
4. Financial Problems: One of the complaints leveled by some criminologists is that female offenders are overlooked in research on offending. One claim made by some theorists is that female offenders are more likely to offend due to financial difficulty. This variable may help determine whether this is the case.
5. Reliance upon social assistance: This could be used as a control. People who are on social assistance may not be able to work.

6. Attitude supportive of crime: One of the messages from the desistance research is that desistance is a decision. Is this decision measurable?

Equipment

The data were analyzed using SPSS 13 for Windows.

Research Design

This study is a retrospective analysis of secondary data. The data were collected in two waves at approximately six-month intervals. The data measuring the dependent variable, conviction and/or probation violation, was collected by the court system.

Procedure

A logistic regression was performed because of the dichotomous nature of the independent variable. The main effect variables were TotCrim, ClientAge, Race, Sex, Employment Status, LostJob, GotJob, and HadJob. Interaction terms TotCrimXlj, TotCrimXgj, and TotCrimXhj were added in a second step in the model.

RESULTS

The results of step one of the regression output were as shown in Table 1 and plotted in Figure 2. Loosing a job is about the same as never having a job. Offenders who get a job are slightly less likely to have a violation than offenders with no job, and offenders who are employed at both time periods are least likely to have a violation.

Table 1

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status.

B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)		
						Lower	Upper	
Prev. Off.	0.051	0.010	25.766	1	0.000	1.052	1.032	1.073
Lost Job	-0.020	0.222	0.008	1	0.927	0.980	0.635	1.513
Got a Job	-0.457	0.184	6.179	1	0.013	0.633	0.441	0.908
Has Job	-0.922	0.169	29.890	1	0.000	0.398	0.286	0.554
Constant	-0.920	0.149	38.131	1	0.000	0.399		

Step 1: -2 Log likelihood: 1318.49, Cox & Snell R Square: 0.059, Nagelkerke R Square: 0.085

Figure 2

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status.

The results of step two of the regression output were as shown in Table 2 and plotted in Figure 3. The interaction with prior offending results in offenders with high numbers of previous offenses becoming substantially more likely to offend if they get or lose a job, and substantially less likely to offend if they have and keep a job.

Table 2

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status with interaction terms showing the impact of previous offenses on job status.

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Prev. Off.	0.013	0.011	1.307	1	0.253	1.013	0.991	1.035
Lost Job	-0.233	0.353	0.434	1	0.510	0.792	0.396	1.584
Got a Job	-0.983	0.281	12.232	1	0.000	0.374	0.216	0.649
Has Job	-1.678	0.255	43.341	1	0.000	0.187	0.113	0.308
TotCrimXlj	0.023	0.033	0.474	1	0.491	1.023	0.959	1.092
TotCrimXgj	0.060	0.024	6.040	1	0.014	1.062	1.012	1.114
TotCrimXhj	0.090	0.023	15.918	1	0.000	1.094	1.047	1.143
Constant	-0.577	0.155	13.892	1	0.000	0.561		

Step 2: -2 Log likelihood: 1302.01, Cox & Snell R Square: 0.072, Nagelkerke R Square: 0.104

Figure 3

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status with interaction terms showing the impact of previous offenses on job status.

The results shown above may have been due to low numbers of offenders in the high ranges and so the mean number of new offenses was plotted by number of offenses and placed in Figure 4. The trend is fairly clear up to about 15 offenses and then starts to fall apart after that. The data was recoded to reflect the low numbers in the higher ranges by transforming all values between 0-15 into the same variable and then coding all values above 15 into the number 16.

Figure 4.

Mean Number of New Offenses Plotted by Previous Offenses

The plot in Figures 5 and 6 show the resulting output from Steps 1 and 2 of the new logistic regression model.

Table 3

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status.

B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
						Lower	Upper
Prev. Off.	0.110	0.015	54.348	1	0.000	1.117	1.084 1.150
Lost Job	-0.030	0.224	0.017	1	0.895	0.971	0.626 1.506
Got a Job	-0.464	0.186	6.206	1	0.013	0.629	0.436 0.906
Has Job	-0.907	0.171	28.315	1	0.000	0.404	0.289 0.564
Constant	-1.333	0.172	60.427	1	0.000	0.264	

Step 1: -2 Log likelihood: 1291.496, Cox & Snell R Square: 0.081, Nagelkerke R Square: 0.116

Table 4

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status with interaction terms showing the impact of previous offenses on job status.

B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
						Lower	Upper
Prev. Off.	0.068	0.025	7.454	1	0.006	1.070	1.019 1.123
Lost Job	-0.245	0.482	0.259	1	0.611	0.782	0.304 2.012
Got a Job	-0.849	0.369	5.300	1	0.021	0.428	0.208 0.881
Has Job	-1.626	0.338	23.158	1	0.000	0.197	0.101 0.381
TotCrimXlj	0.026	0.055	0.230	1	0.632	1.027	0.922 1.143
TotCrimXgj	0.048	0.040	1.450	1	0.229	1.049	0.970 1.134
TotCrimXhj	0.090	0.036	6.205	1	0.013	1.095	1.019 1.175
Constant	-0.990	0.230	18.456	1	0.000	0.372	

Step 2: -2 Log likelihood: 1285.137, Cox & Snell R Square: 0.086, Nagelkerke R Square: 0.123

Figure 5

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status.

Figure 6

Probability of offending based on previous number of offenses and change in job status with interaction terms showing the impact of previous offenses on job status.

